

Introduction

This survey is to empower stakeholders to self-identify how they will be represented in the National Open Access Monitor.

The survey expects one response from each stakeholder entity. If multiple responses are obtained and inconsistencies occur, the Project Manager will follow up directly with respondents to clarify.

Throughout this survey:

- The National Open Access Monitor, Ireland will be referred to as *the Monitor*
- Research Performing Organisations will be referred to as *RPOs* and Research Funding Organisation will be referred to as *RFOs*.

If you have any questions relating to this survey, or require assistance in filling it out, please contact Catherine.ferris@mu.ie

[section on identifying the contributor, confirming consent, etc – as with previous survey. Notify respondents that wish their identity to be [pseudonymised](#) that while (a) their answers to this section will be [pseudonymised](#); the organisation they represent will be identifiable through their responses in the rest of the survey due to the nature of the survey.]

Question: are you representing a Publisher? Clicking yes will skip you straight to Section 4 to submit your Persistent Identifiers.

Yes/no

Section 1

RPO & RFO Dashboards

The National Open Access Monitor will include dashboards for each RPO and RFO. [The dashboards will be automatically created for all Irish organisations represented in the OpenAIRE Graph metadata.](#)
<https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/data-model/entities/organization>

Commented [GU1]: Should this link to the list of Irish orgs in Openaire Graph? Or do you want a return from everyone anyway?

Commented [CF2R1]: The aim is a return from everyone - and to identify if there are RPOs and RFOs in Ireland not currently represented in the OpenAIRE graph.

- Comprehensive insights into each Irish RPO's and RFO's activities and OS performance
- **Indicators View**
 - Highlighting **OA uptake** indicators, enables **cross RPO/RFO** benchmarking
 - Offers detailed **breakdowns** and **filtering**
- **Research Outputs View**
 - Facilitate **browsing**, standard and advanced **searching**, and **filtering**
- **RPO/RFO Managers**
 - Access to the **Sandbox** to verify data quality (e.g., if a new repository is harvested, deduplication in OpenORGS, etc.)
 - Access to **OpenORGS** tool to deduplicate organization name (RPOs)

The questions in this section are to (a) ensure we have a complete list of Irish RPOs and RFOs, ~~and~~ (b) to ensure that we can identify each organisation missing from the OpenAIRE Graph metadata and (c) to ensure each organisation is categorised correctly. ~~This will impact which category of dashboard for your organisation in the Monitor.~~

In the next section, please select the organisation you represent, and indicate if it is an RPO, an RFO, both an RFO and RPO, or neither.

List of organisations: instruction to select (+ include an option "if your organisation is not listed, please add here")

Questions with tick boxes:

RPO

RFO

RPO & RFO

My organisation is neither a RPO or an RFO.

Section 2

Publicly Funded Organisations

As per the tender requirements, the Monitor must identify publicly funded research outputs.

Item	Requirement	Mandatory / Desirable
B1	The Monitor MUST show to what extent Irish scholarly publications resulting from publicly funded research are immediately openly available by default and are accessible on an ongoing basis. Publicly funded in this context is defined as “Publicly funded research is research undertaken in whole or in part via publicly funded resourcing or remuneration, e.g., salaries, grants, contracts, etc.”	M

Publicly funded, in this context, was defined in the National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030.

20 Publicly funded research is research undertaken in whole or in part via publicly funded resourcing or remuneration, e.g. salaries, grants, contracts, etc.

Therefore, the following will be identified as “publicly funded” research outputs in the Monitor:

- all research outputs by staff of publicly funded organisations, and
- all research outputs from grants, partially or fully, funded by a publicly funded Irish funders

In the next section, please identify if your organisation is in receipt of public funding.

Question

Is your organisation in receipt of public funding:

To note: if your organisation is partially funded by public funding and partially funded by other means, select yes.

Yes

No

Section 3

Affiliated Organisations

It is acknowledged that many research organisations in Ireland are formally affiliated, either as a parent/child entities under a parent legal entity, or due to formal research agreements which mean that research outputs from Entity A should also be attributed to Entity B. In the Monitor, these relationships will be reflected in the following way: the research outputs of Entity A will appear on the dashboard of Entity A and also on the dashboard of Entity B. Your input is required here, as the experts in the complex legal relationships your organisation has, to define what is the appropriate representation of those organisations’ research outputs in the Monitor.

There are multiple scenarios which may be represented by the Monitor:

Commented [FC3]: The scenarios outlined below are very word (albeit necessarily so). Would a diagrammatic representation help? e.g. Venn

Commented [CF4R3]: Will implement.

- one-to-one relationships: e.g. *Research Centre, which is a Research Performing Organisation, but is not a legal entity. That Research Centre sits under a Higher Education Institution, which is the legal entity for the Research Centre. In this example, the Research Centre will have a RPO Dashboard, and the research outputs of the Research Centre will also appear in the Higher Education Institution dashboard.*
- one-to-many relationships: e.g. *two Research Centres, both Research Performing Organisations, but not legal entities. Those two Research Centres sit under one Higher Education Institution, with is the legal entity for the Research Centres. In this example, both Research Centres will have RPO Dashboards, and the research outputs of both Research Centres will also appear in the Higher Education Institution dashboard.*
- Many-to-many relationships: e.g. *Research Centre, which itself is a Research Performing Organisation, but is not a legal entity. That Research Centre sits under a Higher Education Institution, which is the legal entity for the Research Centre. This Higher Education Institution also has a research agreement with a hospital, ~~where some hospital researchers are affiliated with the Higher Education Institution~~. The same hospital also has a research agreement with Higher Education Institution 2, ~~where some hospital researchers are affiliated with Higher Education Institution 2~~. In this example, the Research Centre will have a RPO Dashboard, and the Hospital will have an RPO dashboard, the research outputs of the Research Centre will also appear on the dashboard of Higher Education Institution 1, and the research outputs of the Hospital will also appear in the applicable Higher Education Institution 1 dashboard, or Higher Education Institution 2 dashboard.*

These examples are not exhaustive, but are indicative examples to help you complete the following section.

Important:

1. This survey expects responses from each entity in the one-to-one, one-to-many, and many-to-many relationships. Only where all entities agree there is a formal relationship in place that should be reflected in the Monitor will the link be implemented. To enable this verification process, please forward this survey to the relevant staff within the other entities for them to complete.
2. This section of the survey is to represent relationships between RPO-to-RPO and RFO-to-RFO, not RPO-to-RFO; research outputs of an RPO funded by an RFO will appear in both dashboards automatically.

Question:

Please select the other organisation(s) that your organisation is formally affiliated to, either as parent/child entities under a parent legal entity, or due to formal research agreements, as part of a one-to-one, one-to-many or many-to-many relationship.

(To note: do not enter your organisation here, you've already selected your organisation in Question 1)

[provide list - include an option "if the organisation is not listed, please add here"]

Please indicate:

- *Do you expect the selected organisation(s) to appear in your organisation's dashboard*
- *Do you expect your organisation to appear in the selected organisation(s)' dashboard(s)*

Commented [GU5]: I don't understand the intention with this one - but I may be missing the point. Are we detailing any hospitals some of our staff may have joint affiliation with? How will the outputs be identified if it's down to the individual researcher rather than the research centre which HE the affiliation is with? Wouldn't you just have to rely on the author using two affiliations in any paper and it being picked up that way?

Commented [CF6R5]: The intention here is to capture FORMAL agreements between organisations, to provide that detail to OpenAIRE so that they can identify and solve any issues that arise in identifying which Dashboards those outputs should appear on. I'll clear up the language to reflect.

Commented [GU7]: Will organisations need a PID to be included?

Commented [CF8R7]: I don't expect this detail from OpenAIRE until the 'National Open Access Report, Ireland' is delivered.

The aim of this survey is to ensure that we capture all organisation PIDs to ensure that OpenAIRE have that data to query the OpenAIRE Graph.

To note: it was a requirement of the tender that the Monitor defines "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata"

Please indicate if, to the best of your knowledge, your organisation is one entity in a many-to-many relationship (see example above), as this will require additional analysis to ensure that research outputs are attributed to the correct RPOs.

Section 4

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

[for Publisher that skipped to this section, include question on capturing name of Publisher to associate with PID]

The tender requirements for the Monitor specified that the vendor must use PIDs to identify Irish scholarly publications: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8169395>

M6	<p>The Monitor MUST, at a minimum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of "open access": "By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself." https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/ • Use the Unpaywall definition of "open access types". • Initially focus on monitoring peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedings • Have the potential in the future to expand to monitor monographs, book chapters, other scholarly publication outputs, open research activities and measures (to be defined during Action 6.2.3, expected in 2025-2027) • Focus on publications which can be uniquely and unambiguously identified by a DOI. • Define an "Irish scholarly publication" as a publication which contains the unique persistent identifier of an Irish organisation in the publication and/or the publication metadata and/or the persistent identifier metadata. 	Compliant (Yes / No)
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The Monitor will be built using open data from the OpenAIRE Graph.

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DATA BACKBONE: THE OPENAIRE GRAPH

- **A Scientific Knowledge Graph**
 - Timely and comprehensive coverage of research outputs
 - 129K data sources, 3M projects, and 235M research outputs (publications, software, datasets, other research products)
 - Near monthly updates
- **Precision, depth & processing**
 - Rigorous cleaning, deduplication, and enrichment for optimal accuracy
 - Enriched metadata links: Research results to projects, author affiliations, and classifications (FoS, SDG)
 - Techniques for duplicate identification in addition to OpenAIRE's curation tools
- **Robustness & openness**
 - Maintenance, load balancing, backups, overseen by the OpenAIRE technology centre
 - Open data & transparent methodologies

graph.openaire.eu

National Open Access Monitor, Ireland | 1st Stakeholder Webinar | 22 September 2023

This section is to capture the PIDs that represent the RPOs, RFOs and Publishers that will be represented in the Monitor, to enable OpenAIRE to query the OpenAIRE graph using those PIDs and identify research outputs associated with your organisation.

Please supply the most comprehensive listing of the following identifiers that you have available to you:

- ROR
- RINGGOLD
- GRID
- ISNI
- For RFOs only: Open Funder Registry (previously known as the Crossref Funder Registry, or FundRef)
- For Publishers only: ISSNs, e-ISSNs, ISSN-L

If your organisation is one entity in a one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many relationship [include description from above, for publishers], please only supply the PIDs that identify your discreet RPO, RFO, or Publisher entity. To enable a comprehensive collation of relevant PIDs for this process, please forward this survey to the relevant staff within the other affiliated entities for them to complete their PID submission.